

NEWSLETTER ON SERIALS PRICING ISSUES

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196.1 COST EFFECTIVENESS OF SECONDARY SERVICES

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Recently, a US court has decided in favour of AIP in the suit filed by Gordon & Breach about an article in *Physics Today* which compared the cost of scientific journals in terms of cents per word. A large number of scientists and scholars in the developing countries depend on secondary services for their survival, as their institutions cannot afford the huge costs of subscriptions to journals. [The best academic library in India - - the J R D Tata Memorial Library at the Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore -- receives about 2,000 serials. In the US many universities receive more than 50,000 serials.] It will help Third World scientists, scholars and their institutions if a detailed study could be made of the cost effectiveness of secondary services (such as *Chemical Abstracts*, *BIOSIS*, *Compendex Plus*, *Science Citation Index*, *Physics Abstracts*, *Sociological Abstracts*, *Social Science Citation Index*, etc.). Of course, cost by itself would not mean much; the study should also look at the quality of the information provided, the speed with which each service covers the primary literature, ease of access, special features, and such other factors. I do not know if such a study is already available. If it is not, it should be carried out and the results publicised widely.

For example, one would like to know the total number of journals indexed cover-to-cover, the total number of papers/review articles/letters abstracted in a year, cost per abstract, time lag between the appearance of an article in a primary journal and the appearance of its abstract in the secondary service, and so on.

I wonder if any librarian or a scientometricist (who has access to most of the databases to be studied) would be interested in such a study.

I would like to hear from interested scholars.